

FORMATION OF COMPETENCES OF STUDENTS IN TEACHING INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN PROFESSIONAL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract. The formation of information technology education competencies among students becomes an important task of professional educational institutions. In this article we will consider the main aspects of this problem.

Key words: professional educational institutions, information technology, basic computer and software, programming languages, approaches, teaching methods, modern teaching methods.

ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ КОМПЕТЕНЦИЙ СТУДЕНТОВ ПРИ ПРЕПОДАВАНИИ ИНФОРМАЦИОННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНЫХ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫХ УЧРЕЖДЕНИЯХ

Аннотация. Формирование у студентов образовательных компетенций в области информационных технологий становится важной задачей профессиональных образовательных учреждений. В этой статье мы рассмотрим основные аспекты этой проблемы.

Ключевые слова: профессиональные образовательные учреждения, информационные технологии, базовые компьютерные технологии и программное обеспечение, языки программирования, подходы, методы обучения, современные методы преподавания.

It is known that at present information technologies occupy a key place in all spheres of activity, including education. Therefore, the formation of information technology education competencies among students becomes an important task of professional educational institutions. In this article we will consider the main aspects of this problem.

Today, information technology is penetrating all areas of education, creating new opportunities for learning, research and communication. They help improve access to knowledge, create conditions for independent learning, develop information literacy of students, and develop critical thinking.

Information technology plays an important and transformative role in education. They permeate all aspects of the educational process, from teaching materials and communication to the management of educational institutions. Here are some of the key roles of information technology in education:

Access to knowledge: information technology provides access to a huge amount of knowledge and information from various sources. With the help of the Internet, students can research relevant materials, learn from leading experts in their fields, and explore online courses and resources that complement and expand the curriculum.

Improving the learning process: Information technology provides tools and resources that make the learning process more interactive, interesting and effective. E-textbooks, multimedia materials, interactive lessons and online platforms provide flexibility and a personalized learning approach to suit different learning styles and paces of students.

Modern teaching methods: Allows you to use new methods and approaches in teaching information technology. This includes using virtual and augmented reality to create immersive

learning environments, using games to increase student motivation, and facilitating online collaboration for collaborative learning and teamwork.

Developing the skills of the future: information technology helps students develop the skills needed in today's information society. This includes digital literacy, critical thinking, problem solving, communication and collaboration skills. The use of information technology in education provides students with practical skills that they can use in their future professional lives.

Students studying in vocational education institutions must acquire certain competencies in order to effectively use information technology in their professional activities. Some key competencies include:

- basic computer and software skills;
- understanding the principles of the network and the Internet;
- the ability to search, evaluate and use information from various sources;
- ability to work with special programs for electronic documents and data processing;
- the ability to effectively use e-mail, social networks and other means of communication;
- knowledge of the basic principles of information security and data protection.

Basic computer and software skills are fundamental to the effective use of information technology. Here are some of these abilities:

Operating system. It is the ability to understand and work with a computer operating system (eg Windows, Linux). This includes skills such as managing files and folders, installing and removing programs, configuring the system, and so on.

Working with text editors. It forms the ability to create, edit and format text documents using programs such as Microsoft Word, Google Docs or Libre Office Writer. Important skills include images, tables, styles, and page layout.

Spreadsheets. These are Microsoft Excel, Google Docs or Libre Office. They form the ability to work with spreadsheet programs. Skills include creating tables, entering data, using formulas and functions to analyze and manipulate data, creating charts, and more.

Presentation program. It develops presentation software skills such as Microsoft PowerPoint, Google Slides or Libre Office Impress. Students will be required to create presentations using various slides by adding text, images, videos, animations and transition effects.

Internet and e-mail. It builds skills in using the browser to search for information on the Internet, work with e-mail, including writing and sending messages, attaching files, organizing folders and filters to manage the mailbox.

Security and data protection. This requires an understanding of the basic principles of information security, including creating strong passwords, protecting data, knowing the types of Internet threats, and taking precautions when working online.

These are the basic computer and software skills that students need to master in order to use information technology effectively in their studies and careers.

Understanding the principles of networking and the Internet is important for students, especially in an information technology environment. Now let's move on to the basic principles that students should know.

Network basics. In doing so, students should understand basic networking concepts such as IP addressing, data transfer protocols (such as TCP/IP), local and wide area networks, routing, and data switching.

Internet. In doing so, students should gain an understanding of the architecture and structure of the Internet, including Internet Service Providers (ISPs), servers, clients, domains, and domain names.

Protocols and services. In doing so, students should be familiar with the basic protocols and services used on networks and the Internet. This includes communication protocols such as HTTP (Hypertext Protocol), FTP (File Transfer Protocol), SMTP (Simple Mail Transfer Protocol), and others.

Network devices. In doing so, students should be familiar with various network devices such as routers, switches, bridges, modems, and wireless access points. It is important to understand how these devices work and how they interact with each other on a network.

Network security. In doing so, students should gain an understanding of the basic principles of network and Internet security. This includes understanding security threats such as viruses, hackers, phishing, and security practices such as firewalls, encryption, authentication, and authorization.

Cloud computing. As cloud technology advances, it is important for students to have an understanding of how cloud computing and services such as cloud storage, virtual machines, and platforms as a service (PaaS) work.

Understanding these principles will help students use networks and the Internet more effectively and safely, as well as interact with various systems and services in the information environment.

The ability to search, evaluate and use information from various sources is a key skill in today's information society. Here are some key aspects of this skill.

1. Students should be able to search for information effectively using a variety of sources. This includes searching the Internet using search engines (such as Google), using digital libraries and databases, accessing specialized resources, and using social media and forums to seek out the experiences of experts and others.

2. It is important to learn how to critically evaluate information in order to determine its reliability, relevance and reliability. Readers should pay attention to source, authorship, fact checking, context, and bias. This helps to avoid low-quality or inaccurate information and use only reliable and trusted sources.

3. When processing large amounts of information, students should be able to select the most relevant and useful information for their goals and objectives. This includes the ability to filter and sort search results, analyze the content and structure of texts, and use keywords and terms for specific searches.

4. Students should be able to effectively use the information received in their work. This includes the ability to cite sources, make bibliographic references, support your arguments, and use information to make informed decisions. The use of information should also take into account copyright and ethical considerations.

5. Information is constantly changing and evolving, so students should develop the habit of constantly updating their knowledge and skills. This includes keeping up with the latest research, publications, and news in your field, as well as attending educational events, conferences, and courses to expand your knowledge horizons.

The ability to search for, evaluate and use information from a variety of sources helps students develop information literacy and successfully perform academic and professional tasks based on reliable and up-to-date information.

The ability to work with special programs for electronic documents and data processing is an integral part of modern professional skills. Here are some key aspects of this skill. First, students should be familiar with Word document creation, editing, and formatting programs such as Microsoft Word, Google Docs, or Libre Office Writer. Skills include creating and formatting text, using styles, adding headings, lists, tables, and adding images. Knowledge of spreadsheet software such as Microsoft Excel, Google Sheets or Libre Office Calc is essential. Skills include creating tables, entering and formatting data, using formulas and functions to calculate and analyze data, creating charts, and applying conditional formatting. Knowledge of programming and scripting fundamentals such as Python or SQL can be important to work with data. Students should be able to write and run scripts to automate tasks, manipulate data, and create simple algorithms.

Depending on the field of study or work, students may need to master special programs and tools for data processing. For example, it could be statistical analysis software, a database, a geographic information system, machine learning, or data visualization. To work effectively with data, it is important to master the basic functions and capabilities of these programs. Modern education and professional activities often require the processing and analysis of large amounts of data. It is useful for students to know the basics of working with databases, use the query language (SQL) to retrieve data, and use tools and methods for processing and analyzing big data, such as Apache Hadoop or Apache Spark.

The ability to work with specialized programs for electronic documents and data processing will help students to effectively manage information, analyze data, create reports and presentations, and solve problems related to data processing and analysis as part of their professional activities.

Conducting trainings and seminars aimed at developing skills in working with information technologies is an important component of vocational education. One of the key aspects that should be taken into account when organizing such events is the definition of the target audience. This will determine who will attend the training or workshop. For example, a beginner's course might focus on basic computer skills, while an advanced course might offer more advanced topics and techniques. The next step is choosing the right study program. It is necessary to develop a program covering various aspects of working with information technology. Most importantly, subjects such as computer basics, software, Internet, information security, spreadsheets, website development, and other technology skills should be included.

Another aspect is interactivity and practical activity. This should focus on creating an interactive learning environment where participants can actively participate and apply what they have learned. Next, you need to use different teaching methods. The use of various teaching methods such as lectures, demonstrations, group assignments, discussions and online courses helps participants to diversify information and engage in the learning process. Provide participants with the necessary resources and materials, such as tutorials, manuals, examples, and templates. This gives them access to modern online resources, educational videos and tools to help them deepen their knowledge and practice.

Another key aspect is the assessment of participants' knowledge and skills at the end of the training or workshop. This allows you to check the effectiveness of training and make the necessary adjustments in further activities. Information technology is constantly evolving, so it is important to keep abreast of the latest trends and updates in this area. Information technology skills development trainings and seminars help students and professionals improve their information literacy and succeed in today's digital society.

Knowledge of the basic principles of information security and data protection is an important component of working with information technology. Here are a few basic principles to keep in mind:

1. The principle of confidentiality. This principle means that information should be available only to those who need it and protected from unauthorized access. This includes the use of passwords, data encryption, access control, and restriction of user rights.

2. The principle of integrity. The principle of integrity means that data must be reliable and immutable. Protection against unauthorized modification or alteration of data may include the use of electronic signatures, checksums, and version control systems.

3. The principle of accessibility. The principle of accessibility ensures that information is available at the right time and in the right place by those who have the right to use it. This includes ensuring system stability, backing up data, and protecting against failures or availability attacks.

4. The principle of authentication. Authentication is used to authenticate users and devices. This includes the use of passwords, biometrics, two-factor authentication, and other identification methods.

5. The principle of authorization. The principle of authorization determines the rights and privileges of users to access information and system resources. Access rights management and separation of powers help prevent unauthorized access and use of data.

6. The principle of backup and recovery. Regular data backups and disaster or disaster recovery plans play an important role in keeping your data secure and protected.

7. The principle of education and awareness. It is important to educate users on the basic principles of information security, to be aware of existing threats and attack methods, and to develop their awareness and vigilance regarding data protection. These are just some of the basic principles of information security and data protection. In today's information society, where data plays an important role, it is important to constantly update knowledge in the field of information security, monitor new trends and threats.

Various methods and approaches can be used in the formation of students' competencies in the field of information technology education in professional educational institutions. Some of them include:

- inclusion in curricula and programs of special courses on information technologies;
- organization of practical classes, laboratory work and projects requiring the use of information technology;
- teaching students to use special programs and tools;
- conducting trainings and seminars aimed at developing skills in working with information technologies;
- Use of modern educational technologies such as electronic textbooks, interactive lessons and online courses.

The formation of students' competencies in the field of information technology education has a number of advantages. This allows students to be competitive in the labor market, as knowledge of information technology skills is a necessary requirement in many areas of professional activity. This helps to improve the quality of education and the learning process by expanding access to educational resources and modern teaching methods. In addition, it contributes to the development of students' critical thinking, independence and self-organization,

makes it possible to effectively use information technology in professional activities to solve problems, automate processes and increase efficiency.

In conclusion, we can say that the formation of students' competencies in teaching information technology is an important area of modern professional education. It allows students to acquire the necessary skills and knowledge for successful professional activities in the digital age. Professional educational institutions should pay due attention to this problem and use various methods and approaches for the effective formation of students' competencies in the field of information technology.

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